

Strategies for Coping with Twitter's "Dark Side": A Transactional Model of Stress and Coping Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Social media's "dark side"—including dis/misinformation and harassment—is increasingly problematic. What strategies do people use to cope with such issues in their daily life? Based on Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (TMSC), this study investigated how individuals cope with such issues on Twitter. An online survey, including the Ways of Coping Questionnaire, was used to analyze 800 US adult Twitter users' coping strategies. The study found Folkman and colleagues' 8-strategy grouping applicable to this context. The top coping strategies were Distancing (e.g., "Went on as if nothing had happened"), Self-Controlling (e.g., "I tried to keep my feelings to myself"), and Planful Problem-Solving (e.g., "I made a plan of action and followed it"). Primary and secondary appraisals were associated with most strategies (7 out of 8). Significant demographic differences were found, especially with Twitter usage frequency and gender. Implications for research and practice are discussed.

KEYWORDS

Social media problems; Coping strategies; Information behavior; Individual differences; Twitter

INTRODUCTION

Background and research gaps

Social media's "dark side", such as dis/misinformation and harassment, is increasingly apparent (Baccarella et al., 2018, Bertazzo, 2021; Suci, 2021). This is alarming as social media is integral to many people's daily lives. While social media gives people a voice on social and political issues (Silver & Clancy, 2022) and supports information seeking, social interaction, and entertainment (Whiting & Williams, 2013), it is also used for cyberbullying and spreading disinformation (McClain et al., 2021). It is thus paramount to understand how people handle social media stressors in their everyday life (Wolfers & Utz, 2022). For example, what strategies do people use to cope with such stressors? Are there individual differences? Having more investigations grounded in established theoretical frameworks will bring broader conceptual perspectives and systematic understandings of coping behaviors on social media. This could inform further research on information literacy training and social media interventions.

We posit that Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (TMSC; Lazarus, 1999; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) and the Ways of Coping Questionnaire (WCQ; developed based on TMSC; Folkman et al., 1986; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) is promising to understand social media users' coping behavior. The broader stress and coping (S&C) literature and TMSC have informed social media research (e.g., Bowditch et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2019; McHugh et al., 2018; Sriwilai & Charoensukmongkol, 2016; Weinstein et al., 2015). To our knowledge, however, no studies have used the whole WCQ to study how people cope with problems on social media (hereafter, *social media coping*). Several conceptual and methodological gaps remain. For instance, S&C- or TMSC-informed research on this area tends to: (a) build a unique model for a specific case and not test the model again in subsequent studies, (b) group coping strategies into broad categories (e.g., problem-focused and emotion-focused), (c) focus on students or youth, or (d) have small sample sizes.

Research objectives and research questions (RQs)

This study seeks to contribute towards bridging the above gaps by applying an established model and a full instrument with more granular coping strategies, focusing on the general adult population with a larger sample size. Beyond empirical findings, this study holds a broader conceptual objective. That is, the study aims to explore the applicability of TMSC and WCQ as a theoretical framework plus measurement instrument combo for larger-scale analyses of social media coping. Specifically, this exploratory study focuses on TMSC's central constructs: coping strategies (operationalized with WCQ) and cognitive appraisal (primary and secondary appraisal). Regarding the social media platform, this study focuses on Twitter, a popular microblog with reportedly 486 million users worldwide and 83.4 million in the US (Kemp, 2022). Twitter is a go-to source for breaking news (Mitchell et al., 2021), where, unfortunately, dis/misinformation and harassment can be rampant (Center for Countering Digital Hate, 2022b; McClain et al., 2021). Overall, with the empirical and conceptual objectives mentioned above, this study investigates: **(RQ1a)** To what extent do participants use the WCQ coping strategies in response to problems on Twitter? **(RQ1b)** Are the coping strategies used to a similar or different extent? **(RQ2)** To what extent are primary appraisal, secondary appraisal, and users' characteristics (age, gender, educational attainment, and Twitter usage frequency) associated with the use of coping strategies?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lazarus and Folkman's TMSC is prominent in S&C research (Biggs et al., 2017). TMSC sees stress as a bi-directional interaction (i.e., transaction) between individuals and the environment. Coping is viewed as context-specific and a dynamic process. TMSC's sensitivities to process, relation, and context align well with prevailing information behavior (IB) paradigms, such as information-seeking in context (Vakkari et al., 1997). Scholars have observed certain coping strategies incorporated in IB (e.g., information avoidance when coping with threatening health information; Case et al., 2005, and withdrawal when dealing with information overload; Savolainen, 2007).

Coping strategies. Folkman and Lazarus's 66-items WCQ asks to what extent a respondent used different strategies (e.g., "Tried to forget the whole thing," "I got professional help") to handle specific stressors. The coping strategies are not mutually exclusive. In terms of analysis, coping strategies from the WCQ are often grouped based on: (a) researchers' own factor analysis on the 66 items, and/or (b) groupings from Folkman et al. (1986) (e.g., 8 groups of strategies, yielded from their community sample [hereafter, *8-strategy grouping*]). WCQ has shown sound internal consistency, construct validity, and test-retest reliability, especially when researchers run their own factor analysis (Lundqvist & Ahlström, 2006; Sørli & Sexton, 2001). The use of extant groupings, however, has yielded mixed results. For instance, a study on work-related stress attempted the 8-strategy grouping and found only 3 of the 8 strategies showed adequate internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha > .7$) (Gaudioso et al., 2017). Researchers posited that due to WCQ's context-specificity, variations in the types and intensity of stressors may have contributed to the mixed results (Sørli & Sexton, 2001). The current study will shed light on whether the 8-strategies grouping yields adequate internal consistency for studying Twitter users' coping strategies.

Influencing factors. TMSC identifies various personal, environmental, and situational factors influencing coping. Central to TMSC is the cognitive appraisal process, which triggers coping behaviors. TMSC differentiates two types: *primary appraisal* and *secondary appraisal*. They were investigated in this study; details are discussed in the Measures section. This initial exploration also studied four personal characteristics: *gender*, *age*, *educational attainment*, and *Twitter usage frequency*. The first three are basic demographics that S&C literature has explored (e.g., gender: Lazarus and Folkman, 1984, Orel et al., 2015; age: Dunkel-Schetter et al., 1992, Gaudioso et al., 2017; education: Dunkel-Schetter et al., 1992). Twitter research has similarly examined these demographics (McClain et al., 2021). Lastly, Twitter usage frequency was included to account for the study context, in which stressors were encountered while using Twitter. Frequent Twitter usage may lead to more exposure to stressors and higher stress levels. But frequent users also may have accumulated more experience to better handle the stressors (Sin, 2016; Sin & Kim, 2014). This study will show if and how the six factors (including 2 appraisal types and 4 individual characteristics) were associated with Twitter coping strategies and their effect sizes.

RESEARCH METHODS

Data collection and sampling

The study's research method is secondary analysis of survey data (Kiecolt & Nathan, 1985). The dataset used here was collected from an online questionnaire about IB on Twitter that we developed and fielded in late 2018. The questionnaire asked about demographics, Twitter usage and IB, including items on TMSC and WCQ. Adult Twitter users in the US were the survey's study population. Participants were recruited from Amazon Mechanical Turk (MTurk), which is known to facilitate the inclusion of diverse samples (Casler et al., 2013). The questionnaire was hosted on Qualtrics and pilot-tested with ten MTurkers before data collection. The survey collected 800 responses. This secondary analysis included the TMSC and WCQ items from all 800 samples.

Measures

Coping strategies. These were measured with WCQ. On a 4-point scale (0 = *not used* to 3 = *used a great deal*), participants indicated the extent to which they used each of the 66 strategies when encountering problematic users/tweets on Twitter. Strategies were grouped in the analysis stage using the 8-strategy grouping (Folkman et al., 1986): (1) Confrontive Coping ("Stood my ground and fought for what I wanted"); (2) Distancing ("Went on as if nothing had happened"); (3) Self-Controlling ("I tried to keep my feelings to myself"); (4) Seeking Social Support ("Talked to someone to find out more about the situation"); (5) Accepting Responsibility ("Criticized or lectured myself"); (6) Escape-Avoidance ("Hoped a miracle would happen"); (7) Planful Problem-Solving ("I made a plan of action and followed it"); and (8) Positive Reappraisal ("Changed or grew as a person in a good way"). Scores in each strategy group were summed and averaged. Their Cronbach's alphas in this study ranged from .70 to .84 (Fig. 1).

Influencing factors. *Primary appraisal* refers to "whether or not what is happening is relevant to one's values, goal commitments, beliefs about self and world, and situational intentions" (Lazarus, 1999, p. 75). Further actions only occur when a person appraises that "something of greater adaptational importance is occurring" (Lazarus, 1999, p. 76). A 5-point scale (1 = *not important at all* to 5 = *extremely important*) measured whether handling Twitter issues was appraised as important ("How important is it for you that the following issues on Twitter be addressed?"). There were four items ("Inaccurate information," "Fake news," "Insensitive, mean, or hurtful information/behavior," and

"Cyberbullying and cyber shaming"). The sample mean of primary appraisal in this study was 3.90 ($SD = 0.97$; $\alpha = .83$). *Secondary appraisal* refers to the assessment of what can be done. It covers whether individuals have a sense of conviction (e.g., self-efficacy) that they can control themselves and environmental conditions to manage a stressful situation (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Following Bandura's (2006) guide on self-efficacy response scales, a Likert-like scale was used (0 = *cannot do at all*, 5 = *moderately can do*, 10 = *highly certain can do*). The question was, "How certain are you that you can do the following?" There were five items ("Verify and fact-check dubious information on Twitter," "Protect your friends and family from problematic Twitter users/tweets," "Solve the issues with problematic Twitter users/tweets yourself," "Influence your friends and family to behave appropriately on Twitter" and "Influence problematic users to behave appropriately on Twitter"). The sample mean was 5.14 ($SD = 1.67$; $\alpha = .71$). *Gender* was measured as a nominal variable, where *age* and *educational attainment* were ordinal. *Twitter usage frequency* used a 5-point Likert-type scale, asking, "In the last six months, how frequently have you tweeted/retweeted?" The answer options can be found in the Respondent demographics section.

Data analysis methods

Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted using R (R Core Team, 2022). Cronbach's alpha was obtained from the *psych* package (Revelle, 2022). For RQ1b, one-way repeated measures ANOVA with Greenhouse-Geisser correction provided within-subjects comparisons of each participant's coping strategies usage. Student's t-tests with the Holm adjustment were used for post-hoc pairwise comparisons (Patil, 2022). RQ2 used multiple regressions (MRs) with robust estimation. MR diagnostics found no multicollinearity issues (VIF: 1.08 to 1.16) (Lüdtke, 2022; Lüdtke et al., 2021). For each MR, the independent variables were primary appraisal, secondary appraisal, gender, age, educational attainment, and Twitter usage frequency. The dependent variable was coping strategy usage.

RESULTS

Respondent demographics

The sample comprised 800 adult Twitter users in the US. Over half were women ($n = 417$, 52.1%). Men constituted 47.6% ($n = 381$) of the sample. Two respondents identified as genderqueer (.25%). Regarding *age*, respondents were in their 30s ($n = 380$, 47.5%), 40s ($n = 168$, 21.0%), 20s ($n = 119$, 14.9%), 50s ($n = 93$, 11.6%) and 60 and above ($n = 40$, 5.0%). *Educational attainment* included: Bachelor's degree ($n = 319$, 40%), some college education ($n = 307$, 38.4%), postgraduate degree ($n = 88$, 11.0%), and higher school degree ($n = 85$, 10.6%). One respondent (.125%) did not indicate their education level. Most were weekly users of Twitter ($n = 259$, 32.4%), followed by daily ($n = 204$, 25.5%), less than monthly ($n = 145$, 18.1%), monthly ($n = 144$, 18.0%), and hourly ($n = 48$, 6.0%) users.

RQ1 results: Coping strategies

Distancing was the most used strategy on average (Fig. 1), followed by: Self-Controlling, Planful Problem-Solving, Confrontive Coping, Positive Reappraisal, and Seeking Social Support. Escape-Avoidance and Accepting Responsibility shared the last spot. The use of these eight strategies showed statistically significant differences, $F(4.93, 3938.45) = 464.70$, $p < .001$, $\omega_p^2 = .19$. The post-hoc pairwise comparisons revealed significant differences in 25 out of 28 pairs (Fig. 1). The only three nonsignificant pairs were: Confrontive Coping vs. Positive Reappraisal, Accepting Responsibility vs. Escape-Avoidance; and Seeking Social Support vs. Positive Reappraisal.

Figure 1. Coping strategies usage: Descriptive statistics and post-hoc pairwise comparisons

RQ2 results: Factors associated with coping strategies usage

The MRs were all statistically significant, with different variables at play (Fig. 2). This section highlights a few findings. First, *primary* and *secondary appraisals* both emerged with many statistically significant relationships (7 out of 8), with higher appraisal scores correlated with more use of a strategy. The nonsignificant association for *primary appraisal* was Accepting responsibility; for secondary appraisal, it was Distancing. Second, *secondary appraisal* often has larger effect sizes (standardized betas) than *primary appraisal* (6 out of 8). Interestingly, the two exceptions were Distancing and Self-Controlling, which happened to be the most used strategies. Third, among the four user characteristics, *Twitter usage frequency* was associated with coping strategies the most (7 strategies; all but Distancing), followed by *gender* (4 strategies), *age* (3 strategies), and *educational attainment* (2 strategies). Fourth, within each strategy, *Twitter usage frequency* (e.g., hourly vs. less than monthly) and *gender* (e.g., genderqueer vs. man) were among the largest effect sizes. It should be noted that the genderqueer group has only two respondents; the above results on *gender* should be interpreted with this caveat in mind. Fifth, when *gender* is significant, both

genderqueer (in Confrontive Coping, Seeking Social Support) and women (in Confrontive Coping and Planful Problem-Solving) used the strategies less than men. Sixth, R^2 showed the variables explained 3.1% to 22% of the variances in strategies. Intriguingly, the two withdrawal types of coping (Distancing and Escape-Avoidance) had the lowest R^2 , while the strategy with the highest R^2 is the one that appears most aggressive, Confrontive Coping.

	Confrontive Coping	Distancing	Self-Controlling	Seeking Social Support	Accepting Responsibility	Escape-Avoidance	Planful Problem-Solving	Positive Reappraisal
Primary appraisal	0.08 *	0.09 *	0.15 ***	0.11 ***	0.05	0.07 *	0.16 ***	0.10 **
Secondary appraisal	0.28 ***	0.06	0.14 ***	0.26 ***	0.17 ***	0.12 **	0.25 ***	0.24 ***
Gender (Reference group: Man)								
Woman	-0.18 **	-0.12	-0.03	0.09	-0.10	-0.09	-0.21 **	0.03
Genderqueer	-1.13 **	0.70	-1.30	-0.77 ***	-0.76	-0.37	-1.16	-1.07 **
Age (Reference group: 20s)								
30s	-0.12	-0.13	-0.05	-0.15	-0.21	-0.15	-0.07	-0.02
40s	-0.11	-0.02	0.01	-0.19	-0.28 *	-0.30 *	-0.04	-0.02
50s	-0.20	0.10	0.09	-0.26	-0.40 **	-0.42 **	-0.01	-0.06
60 and above	-0.10	-0.01	0.16	-0.31 *	-0.32	-0.46 **	0.17	0.18
Educational attainment (Reference group: High school degree)								
Some college	0.10	0.19	0.43 ***	0.12	0.10	0.26 *	0.14	0.15
Bachelor's degree	0.05	0.10	0.31 **	0.08	0.03	0.19	0.14	0.10
Master's degree or above	-0.08	0.14	0.38 *	0.01	0.02	0.26	0.18	0.05
Twitter usage frequency (Reference group: Less than monthly)								
Monthly	0.15	-0.13	0.03	0.16	0.28 **	0.21 *	0.20	0.07
Weekly	0.45 ***	0.04	0.22 *	0.22 *	0.44 ***	0.15	0.31 **	0.23 *
Daily	0.57 ***	-0.06	0.06	0.29 **	0.36 ***	0.18	0.34 **	0.17
Hourly	0.86 ***	0.04	0.36	0.71 ***	0.96 ***	0.74 **	0.68 ***	0.72 ***
<i>F</i>	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -14.70	<i>F</i> (15,783) * -1.68	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -5.10	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -8.66	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -7.68	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -5.03	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -10.31	<i>F</i> (15,783) *** -7.09
<i>R</i> ²	0.220	0.031	0.089	0.142	0.128	0.088	0.165	0.120

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$ *** $p < .001$

Figure 2. Factors and coping strategies: Multiple regressions results (standardized betas)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The first research implication concerns Folkman et al.'s (1986) 8-strategy grouping, for which this study found sound internal consistency. This suggests that not only the WCQ, but also the 8-strategy grouping appear suitable for investigating coping strategies on Twitter. Future studies are needed to verify whether this result would hold and to test WCQ's psychometric properties further in the context of social media coping. The selection of this pre-COVID-19 dataset allowed analyses of people's social media coping without the confounding factors caused by extreme events (e.g., additional information seeking and prolonged stress and anxiety during a worldwide pandemic). Now that many societies have transitioned into a post-pandemic stage, it is of interest to investigate how similar/dissimilar people's social media coping is compared to the pre-pandemic era, such as those found in this study. Second, analyzing more granular strategies can be fruitful. For example, RQ1 found Distancing as the most used and Escape-Avoidance as one of the least used strategies. If the study used broad categories, both strategies would be lumped under the emotion-focused category, for example. Also, RQ2 found that no strategy shares the same set of significant factors. All told, some nuanced findings are likely obscured if broad categories are used. Third, demographic differences were found, some with multiple strategies and large effect sizes. Research on this topic is recommended to include individual characteristics as control variables, if not as main constructs. Fourth, in light of this study's findings on *gender*, and reports on the rise in hate speech on Twitter, especially after the recent ownership change (Center for Countering Digital Hate, 2022a), the coping strategies of gender minorities and other minority groups would be a significant area to explore. Lastly, this exploratory study has certain limitations that future research may address. This study focused on the primary TMSC constructs and four user characteristics. Samples are limited to US adult Twitter users recruited from MTurk, which may not represent broader populations. Future studies may expand the research by including more TMSC constructs and influencing factors. Of particular interest is pinpointing factors related to Distancing, which the current set of factors yielded a low R^2 . Also, TMSC research on other social media platforms with representative samples may be conducted, which will facilitate cross-platform and cross-sample comparisons.

Regarding practical implications, it is quite assuring that Planful Problem-Solving (often viewed as a productive strategy) is among the top three. However, the most-used strategy is Distancing, a strategy often considered emotion-focused and less helpful. This warrants attention. Scholars have qualified that such a strategy may work for certain situations (e.g., when stressors cause significant emotional distress). Still, their benefits are likely short-term (Biggs et al., 2017). Respondents in this study used Distancing and Self-Controlling (which includes keeping things to oneself) the most. These findings signal a need for intervention from researchers, educators, and policymakers.

To conclude, this study provides initial evidence of TMSC's and WCQ's potential for studying how people cope with stressors on Twitter. Research implications and areas for further investigation are discussed. The findings also point to a need for action. To help individuals better cope with social media stressors, concerted efforts to design and test training and intervention campaigns could prove beneficial.

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